

The V2 modifications are listed below.

- Introduction: 'can' was removed and replaced by 'could', and the reference 'EFSA 2020' was added.
The word 'clear' was removed to be more objective.
- In the social enrichments, mirrors section, the word 'behaviour' was replaced by 'activity' and the references 'Jekkel & Milistis, 2009' and 'Edgar and Seaman (2010)' were added.
- The recommendation section was modified accordingly: 'In the case of rabbits that need to be reared alone, such as breeding does, the use of mirrors might reduce the effects of isolation (García, 2020). However, some important social behaviour cannot be performed with the use of mirrors (i.e., inability to perform allo-grooming, resting in group or couple).
- The Physical and structural enrichments's definition has been nuanced adding the verb 'could'.

- In the elevated platforms the reference 'Postollec et al 2028' was added and 'Faekas 2016' was removed.
- This sentence was modified to clarify Trocino et al. 2019 findings: 'In growing rabbits, elevated platforms offer additional opportunities to express species specific behaviours, encouraging physical activity and resting without compromising productivity (Postollec et al., 2008; Matics et al., 2018; Trocino et al., 2019), although an increase in injuries and aggressions can occur (Trocino et al., 2019).'
- Recommendation: the word 'most' was suppressed to be more objective.
- Hiding places : 'higher cages' was added and the reference 'Hansen and Berthelsen, 2000' was too.
- Occupational enrichments: the word 'could' was added to be more objective. The reference 'Elsayed et al., 2024' was deleted.
- Gnawing material: the reference 'Trocino et al 2013' was removed and the sentence was modified according to the review's modification.
'It facilitates the expression of species-specific behaviours such as gnawing (Baumans, 2005; Huang et al., 2021), and reduced biting, licking bars or aggressive behaviours in growing and laboratory rabbits (Princz, 2007; Berthelsen and Hansen, 1999) and improved reactivity level towards a new environment or a new object (Birolo et al., 2022).'
- High stocking density recommendation: the word 'can' was replaced by 'might' to be more objective
- Sensory enrichments: the sentence below was modified for more clarity.
'Few studies on the use of sensory enrichment, such as music, have been published. However, the use of music is a common practice used by many farmers for rabbits to get used to the sound and not be frightened by usual farm noises rabbits. Unfortunately, this is an area that requires more valid scientific information and no recommendation can be given.'
- The full references are available of the V2 of the linked review.